

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-Sulphur Surface Complexes : Part V. The Effect of Combined Sulphur on Sodium-Azide-Iodine Reaction

Balwant Rai Puri and Ram Singh Hazra

Sulphurized charcoals, obtained on treatment with sulphur, hydrogen sulphide, carbon disulphide and sulphur dioxide at 600°, catalyse the sodium azide-iodine reaction in aqueous solution at ordinary temperatures. The results indicate that in the first three treatments the sulphur that is fixed in substitution for oxygen and oxy-hydrogen groups is catalytically more active than that fixed at the unsaturated sites. This suggests the formation of sulphide and hydrosulphide groups in the former case and that of thioethers in the latter. The sulphur that is fixed on treatment with sulphur dioxide shows very high catalytic activity which suggests the formation of sulphoxide and sulphone groups in this case.

The reaction of sodium azide with iodine

is known to be catalysed by sulphide sulphur, soluble or insoluble, organic or inorganic, as well as by thiosulphate and thiol groups but neither by free sulphur nor by sulphur present in ring combination or as sulphite and sulphate structure¹. Boehm, Hofmann and Clauss² as well as Blayden and Patrick³ noted positive response of their sulphurised carbons and took this as an evidence for the presence of sulphide groups in their products. It was thought of interest to study the catalytic effect of sulphurised charcoals obtained on treatment with hydrogen sulphide, carbon disulphide⁴, sulphur and sulphur dioxide at 600°⁵ on the above reaction with a view to get some information regarding the nature of the sulphur groups formed on the fixation of sulphur by the various treatments.

EXPERIMENTAL

Several samples of sulphurised charcoal were prepared by treating sugar charcoals outgassed at 700° as well as at 1000°⁶ with hydrogen sulphide, carbon disulphide⁴, sulphur or sulphur dioxide⁵ at the optimum temperature of 600°. The products, after a prolonged extraction with carbon disulphide in a soxhlet, to remove any physically held sulphur, were examined for their sulphur content⁴ and catalytic performance as described below.

1. F. Feigl, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", Elsevier, London, 1966, p. 219.
2. H. P. Boehm, U. Hofmann and A. Clauss, Proc. Third Carbon Conf. Pergamon Press, 1959, 241.
3. H. E. Blayden and J. W. Patrick, *Carbon*, 1967, 5, 533.
4. B. R. Puri, C. M. Jain and R. S. Hazra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 67.
5. B. R. Puri, A. K. Balwar and R. S. Hazra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 975.
6. B. R. Puri, N. K. Sandle and O. P. Mahajan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4880.

Charcoal (0.5 g., unless otherwise stated) was mixed with 20 ml. of 0.05 *M* iodine in 0.15 *M* aqueous potassium iodide contained in a 50 ml. conical flask having two openings each one of which was provided with a standard joint (B-10). Through these joints, one of the openings was connected to a nitrometer and the other to a bulb slightly bent and fused to the male part of the joint. The flask was placed in a thermostat maintained at 40° ($\pm 0.02^\circ$). Sodium azide (130 mg.) was taken in a small capsule which was placed in the bulb. The bent portion of the bulb was held downward so that the capsule did not drop down. Later, the bulb was rotated so that the bent portion moved upward. The capsule then dropped down and the reaction started. The progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the volume of nitrogen evolved and collected over mercury in a manometer. The reaction mixture was kept stirred by means of a magnetic stirrer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained on using varying amounts of a sulphurised charcoal obtained on treating 700°-outgassed sugar charcoal with hydrogen sulphide at 600°⁴ containing 6.5 millieq. sulphur/g. are plotted in Fig. 1. The results of blanks obtained in the absence of charcoal or in the presence of 0.5 g. of the same charcoal before sulphurization are also included in the same figure. It is seen that the sulphurised product is highly effective in catalysing the reaction. For instance, 0.5 g. of this material can push the reaction to the extent of 67% of completion in 24 hrs. while the same weight of charcoal without sulphur can push the reaction hardly to the extent of 10%.

Fig. 1. Sodium azide-iodine reaction in the presence of different amounts of 700°-outgassed sugar charcoal before and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with hydrogen sulphide.

The magnitude of the reaction during any given interval of time is seen to increase with increase in the amount of the sulphurised charcoal used. It appears that the sulphurised product itself undergoes certain alterations in its fundamental characteristics during the

reaction which affects its catalytic performance. In order to study this aspect a little further, the same charcoal recovered from the reaction mixture, after thorough washing and drying, was used for the second time and again for the third time. The catalytic efficiency decreased considerably when used for the second time (cf. curve, 8) though not much further when used for the third time. The sulphur content remained unchanged but the charcoal gave positive test for nitrogen as well as iodine after the reaction. This may be the cause of fall in catalytic efficiency.

The effect of using 0.5 g. charcoal associated with varying amounts of sulphur obtained on treatment with sulphur at 600° is shown in Fig. 2. It is seen that the catalytic effect increases with increase in the amount of sulphur associated with it upto 4.6 millieq./g. However, when the sulphur content rises to 7.3 millieq./g., the catalytic efficiency falls appreciably, becoming even less than that of the charcoal containing 1.96 millieq./g. of sulphur. It appears that sulphur fixed by addition at the unsaturated sites presumably as highly stable $\begin{matrix} C \\ \diagup \\ C \end{matrix} > S$ structures⁷ which is maximum in the last mentioned sample (c.f. table 1),

Fig. 2. Sodium azide iodine reaction in the presence of 0.5 g. 700°-outgassed sugar charcoal after fixation of varying amounts of sulphur on treatment with sulphur.

is not so effective as that fixed by substitution through interaction with oxygen or oxygen-hydrogen groups as sulphide and hydrosulphide groups. However, since the amount of sulphur fixed by the substitution process also increases side by side with increase in the amount of sulphur fixed by the addition process, it appears that the increasing proportions of stable structures affect adversely even the catalytic performance of the sulphide and hydrosulphide groups.

The results obtained by working with sulphurised products obtained on reacting 1000°-outgassed charcoal with sulphur, hydrogen sulphide and carbon disulphide are plotted in Fig. 3. The magnitude of the reaction in the presence of these sulphurised products is seen

to be considerably smaller in spite of a large amount of combined sulphur. It may be noted that 1000°-outgassed charcoal had very little oxygen or oxy-hydrogen groups, and, therefore, most of the sulphur was fixed by addition at the unsaturated sites giving rise to stable

$\begin{matrix} C \\ \diagdown \\ C \end{matrix} \rangle S$ structures. These observations, therefore, confirm that such structures being similar to thioethers or to those having sulphur in ring combination which are known¹ to act as slow catalysts, are not so effective as the other sulphur groups in catalysing the reaction.

Fig. 3. Sodium azide-iodine reaction in the presence of 0.5 g. 1000°-outgassed sugar charcoal before and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with various sulphurising reagents.

Fig. 4. Sodium azide-iodine reaction in the presence of 0.5 g. 700°-outgassed sugar charcoal after fixation of varying amounts of sulphur on treatment with hydrogen sulphide.

The catalytic performances of the sulphurised products, obtained on treatment of 700°-outgassed sugar charcoal with hydrogen sulphide and carbon disulphide, are shown in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. The results indicate the same trends as those in Fig. 2, discussed earlier. The catalytic activity increases with increase in the amount of sulphur fixed upto a certain limit but when the amount becomes sufficiently high and the unsaturated sites get fully occupied by sulphur, the reaction becomes slow.

Fig. 5. Sodium azide-iodine reaction in the presence of 0.5 g. 700°-outgassed sugar charcoal after fixation of varying amounts of sulphur on treatment with carbon disulphide.

Fig. 6. Sodium azide-iodine reaction in the presence of 0.5 g. 700°-outgassed sugar charcoal after fixation of varying amounts of sulphur on treatment with sulphur dioxide.

The observations recorded above indicate that during the reaction of charcoal with sulphur, hydrogen sulphide and carbon disulphide at 600°, catalytically active sulphide and hydrosulphide groups are formed on the charcoal surface through substitution of oxygen and oxy-hydrogen groups initially present on the surface, along with catalytically not so active $\text{C} > \text{S}$ structures by addition of sulphur at the unsaturated sites initially present on the surface.

The results obtained on using sulphur dioxide-treated products are plotted in Fig. 6. It is seen that these materials are highly reactive. The time required for the completion of any fraction of the reaction is far less now than it was when the sulphurised products obtained on treatment with any other sulphurising reagent were used. Further, the reaction is now carried to over 90% of completion even in such a short time as 7-8 hrs. The magnitude of the reaction, no doubt, decreases slightly when the sulphur content is raised to 10.8

TABLE I

Amounts of sulphur fixed by addition as well as by substitution on treatment of 700°-outgassed sugar charcoal with sulphur, using different charcoal to sulphur ratios, at 600°.

Total Sulphur fixed (millieq./g.)	Surface unsaturation (Bromine value) (millieq./g.)		Sulphur fixed by addition process (millieq./g.)	Sulphur fixed by substitution process (millieq./g.)
	Before treatment	After treatment		
1	2	3	4 (2-3)	5 (1-4)
1.96	3.8	3.4	0.4	1.56
3.00	3.8	2.7	1.1	1.90
4.60	3.8	1.8	2.0	2.80
7.30	3.8	nil	3.8	3.50

millieq./g. This may, again, be due to the formation of $\text{C} > \text{S}$ structures by addition process.

These results support the view⁷ that most of the sulphur fixed on treatment with sulphur dioxide exists as the reactive sulfoxide and sulphone groups.

Department of Chemistry,
Panjab University,
Chandigarh.

Received April 17, 1969
Revised MSS received December 22, 1969